

Article

Soil C-CO₂ Emissions Across Different Land Uses in a Peri-Urban Area of Central Croatia

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Abstract

Soils play an important role in the global carbon cycle by storing organic carbon and releasing carbon dioxide (CO₂) through biological processes. Land use management practices influence soil CO₂ emissions by changing physical, chemical, and biological soil properties. Seasonal soil C-CO₂ emissions (soil CO₂ efflux expressed as C-CO₂ in kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) were analyzed under cropland, orchard, grassland, forest, and abandoned land, in a peri-urban area in central Croatia in 2021 and 2023. Emissions were measured using the static method in a closed chamber, accompanied by measurements of soil temperature, moisture, and total porosity. In both years, grassland and orchards had the highest average soil C-CO₂ emissions, whereas cropland showed consistently lower values. However, total soil C-CO₂ emissions were significantly lower in 2023, probably influenced by higher precipitation and changes in soil moisture. The seasonal trends differed from year to year, with the highest emissions recorded in fall 2021 and spring 2023. In both years, there was a positive correlation between average soil C-CO₂ emissions and soil temperature/moisture, while soil porosity also contributed to the observed emission variations. The results show the significant influence of land use types on soil C-CO₂ emissions and emphasize the importance of seasonal and environmental factors in assessing soil carbon cycling. This research enhances understanding of soil contributions to climate change and supports the development of sustainable land management practices aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

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1. Introduction

Soil is a key component of the global carbon cycle, acting simultaneously as a dynamic source and sink for carbon dioxide (CO₂)—the most abundant anthropogenic greenhouse gas in terms of both total emissions and cumulative contribution to global warming [1–3]. Globally, soils store more than twice as much carbon as the atmosphere [4] and even small changes in soil carbon stocks can have an impact on atmospheric CO₂ concentrations [5,6]. The ability of soil to store or release carbon is determined by a combination of physical, chemical, and biological processes, many of which are directly influenced by land use and management [7,8]. The way in which the land is managed impacts autotrophic respiration by plant roots and associated symbionts, as well as the level of heterotrophic respiration by soil microbes that decompose organic matter [9–11]. In intensively managed agricultural systems, these biological processes are usually intensified, which accelerates the mineralization of organic matter and increases CO₂ emissions. In contrast, land uses that

maintain continuous vegetation cover and avoid mechanical disturbance, such as forests or established grasslands, favor the stabilization of carbon in the soil and reduce gaseous losses to the atmosphere [12–14]. Anthropogenic activity can modify soil properties such as organic carbon content, pH, nutrient availability, porosity, and biological activity [15–17]. Among these, total porosity is particularly important, as it influences the balance between air, water and soil [18,19]. Soils with higher porosity generally have improved aeration and gas diffusion capacity, which can increase microbial activity and consequently influence CO₂ emission rates [20,21]. Conversely, compacted or poorly structured soils can limit oxygen availability, alter microbial pathways and reduce or divert carbon fluxes [22,23]. However, it is important to emphasize that higher porosity should not be viewed as a limitation; on the contrary, it is a key indicator of good soil structure and overall soil quality. Beyond its role in gas exchange, porosity regulates water infiltration and retention, facilitates root growth, and sustains nutrient cycling, thereby contributing to long-term soil productivity [24]. Thus, while greater porosity may under certain conditions be associated with enhanced CO₂ efflux, it remains an essential attribute of healthy and resilient soils. The pore system can alter soil temperature and moisture, key drivers of CO₂ release [7,25,26]. However, the interaction between these factors can be complex, where many studies have reported varying results regarding their individual and combined effects on soil CO₂ emissions [27–29]. These physical differences between land use systems accumulate over time and affect the long-term ability of the soil to store or release carbon. Intensive land uses, such as fertilized and frequently tilled croplands, often lead to a reduction in soil organic carbon [30,31]. In contrast, less intensively managed systems—such as forests, grasslands or abandoned agricultural land—are more likely to retain organic carbon and gradually promote its incorporation into stable soil fractions [32]. Due to their perennial vegetation, orchard management also has a strong influence on carbon and dynamics in soil [33]. Several previous studies have shown the relationship between land use and soil CO₂ emissions and confirmed the influence of vegetation type, management intensity, and seasonal dynamics. However, most of these studies were conducted over shorter time periods and focused on fewer land use categories, highlighting the need for more comprehensive, multi-seasonal assessments [34–38]. While these processes are widely recognized, there is still limited understanding of how soil CO₂ emissions vary with land use, especially in peri-urban areas where changes are evolving rapidly. This knowledge is essential for making better land use decisions and responding to climate challenges. In this study, the seasonal soil C-CO₂ emissions of five different land use types—cropland, orchard, grassland, forest and abandoned land—in a peri-urban area in central Croatia are investigated over two measurement years. Furthermore, this research is the first study in Croatia to directly quantify soil CO₂ emissions under different land use types in real field conditions. Due to the absence of national measurements, greenhouse gas inventories in Croatia have so far relied on default IPCC emission factors derived from other countries. Developing country-specific emission factors is one of the key IPCC recommendations for improving the accuracy of greenhouse gas reporting. Therefore, this study provides an important contribution to filling this national data gap.

The study takes into account seasonal variations and the influence of environmental factors such as soil temperature and soil moisture, as well as total porosity. The specific objectives of this study are: (1) to compare and quantify soil C-CO₂ emissions in five different land use types; (2) to evaluate the seasonal differences in emission patterns in two consecutive years; and (3) to evaluate the influence of soil temperature, soil moisture, and total porosity on soil C-CO₂ emissions under different land use types.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The field experiment was conducted in 2021 at the Šašincev lighthouse (45.8215° N; 16.1520° E; 121 m a.s.l.), in Zagreb City, Central Croatia (Figure 1). The study area is characterized as predominantly flat and a major part has been continuously cultivated for over a century. It represents a typical agricultural landscape, with annual croplands and surrounding forested areas as the main land use types. Commonly grown crops include winter wheat, maize, soybean, barley, and oats. The experimental station encompasses a total area of 77 ha.

Figure 1. Study location with five different land uses (from left to right: 1—orchard; 2—grassland; 3—abandoned land; 4—cropland; 5—forest).

The basic description of mechanical, physical, and chemical soil properties classified as Stagnosol for each land use is presented in Table 1.

For characterizing and illustrating the average climatic conditions of the study area, data from the meteorological station Maksimir [39], were used for the reference period 2000–2020, as well as the study years 2021 and 2023. The average annual temperature (°C) and total annual precipitation (mm) for the study period (2021–2023) and the reference period (2000–2020) are shown in Figure 2. According to Köppen’s climate classification, the climate is “Cfbw_x”—moderately warm and rainy, consistent with the broader continental climate of the inland Croatian region [40]. In 2021, total precipitation was 772.2 mm. May had the most precipitation (124.0 mm) and June the least (13.2 mm). The average annual

temperature was 12.2 °C, with January being the coldest month (2.8 °C) and July the warmest (24.0 °C). In 2023, total precipitation increased to 1220.2 mm. The wettest month was January (155.7 mm) and February was the driest (35.4 mm). The average annual temperature was 13.3 °C, with February being the coldest month (4.2 °C) and July the warmest month (23.5 °C). Compared to the reference period (2000–2020), in which the average annual temperature was 12.2 °C, 2023 was warmer, with a deviation of +1.1 °C, while the investigated year, 2021, was equal to the reference period. Precipitation in 2021 was lower than the long-term average (−11%), while in 2023, it was well above the reference average (+41%).

Table 1. Soil properties on the experimental field in Šašinovec, Zagreb (TOC—total organic carbon (g/kg); pH—soil reaction in KCl (1:5 *w/w*); EC—electrical conductivity (dS/m); P₂O₅—available phosphorus (mg/kg); Exch. K—exchangeable potassium (mg/kg); Ntotal—total nitrogen (g/kg)).

Soil Properties	Forest	Cropland	Grassland	Orchard	Abandoned
TOC [g/kg]	28.5	13.8	22.7	15.5	22.0
pH in KCl (<i>w/w</i> 1:5)	4.43	7.35	8.30	8.50	6.34
EC [dS/m]	0.050	0.071	0.151	0.129	0.053
P ₂ O ₅ [mg/kg]	45.2	41.8	45.4	81.5	56.2
Exch. K [mg/kg]	43.7	88.7	118.3	159.0	75.3
Ntotal [g/kg]	2.25	1.55	2.79	1.98	2.31
Bulk density [g/cm ³]	0.92	1.32	1.14	1.31	1.15
Sand [%]	9.5	5.8	16.2	8.8	6.8
Silt [%]	80.0	81.5	72.8	79.3	78.2
Clay [%]	10.5	12.8	11.0	11.9	15.0

Figure 2. Monthly precipitation amount (mm) and mean temperature (°C) throughout the reference period (2000–2020) and investigated 2021 and 2023.

2.2. Experimental Design and Management

Of the total 77 ha of the lighthouse, 63 ha are earmarked for research purposes. The study covers five different types of land use: orchard, cropland, grassland, forest, and abandoned agricultural land. Within the trial area, orchard cover 1.1 ha, grassland 0.5 ha, cropland 11 ha, forest 50 ha, and abandoned land 1 ha. The orchard is a conventional apple orchard characterized using mineral fertilizers, plant protection measures, and a structured pruning system (vase training). Management practices include mulching, low soil disturbance, permanent cover, cropping and targeted fertilization. The grassland, established in 1996, is dominated by grass-clover mixtures and managed using sustainable practices. It maintains a permanent vegetation cover without any soil disturbance.

Biomass is mechanically mowed three to four times per season using an Ariens Ikon x52 mower (AriensCo, Brillion, SAD) and left on the surface, serving as mulch and a natural nutrient source. This approach—combining mulching, undisturbed soil, and continuous cover—supports and preserves high soil health. The forest is a long-established deciduous ecosystem, made up of native species like *Quercus petraea* and *Robinia pseudoacacia*. It has been used as forest for over 200 years, without anthropogenic impact. The nutrient cycle is sustained naturally through the decomposition of leaf litter and woody biomass, enabling the gradual accumulation of organic matter in the topsoil. Abandoned agricultural land that has not been farmed for around two decades has been reforested naturally. These areas show no current soil disturbance and serve as a reference for understanding the processes of secondary succession and soil recovery after agricultural abandonment. Before abandonment, the area was conventionally farmed by the previous owner using a winter wheat–maize rotation, typical of intensive arable systems in the region. The cropland has been under conventional management since 2007 and reflects typical regional arable farming systems. Crop rotation includes winter wheat, barley, oats, soybean, and maize. Management practices involve intensive mineral fertilization, annual plowing, as well as the regular use of herbicides and insecticides. The system lacks conservation measures such as organic fertilization, cover cropping, and mulching. Detailed agro-technical measures for cropland and orchard land uses are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Agro-technical measures and crop information for cropland and orchard.

Land Use	Year	Crop Type	Fertilization	Plant Protection	Sowing/Harvest
Orchard	-	Apple orc.	200 kg ha ⁻¹ NPK 15-15-15 (fall)	-Fungicide: Copper (I) hydroxide 100 g L ⁻¹ + Paraffin oil 550 g L ⁻¹ ; 4 L ha ⁻¹ (NOVAG AGROCHEMICALS, Novaki, Croatia)	-
Cropland	2021	Soybean	300 kg ha ⁻¹ NPK 7-20-30	-Herbicide: Frontier X2 1 L ha ⁻¹ (Dimetenamid-p 720 g L ⁻¹) (BASF, Ludwigshafen, Germany) + Senat WG 0.5 kg ha ⁻¹ (Metribuzin 700 g kg ⁻¹) (UPL Europe Ltd., Warrington, UK) + Clematis 0.3 L ha ⁻¹ (Klomazon 360 g L ⁻¹) (ALBAUGH TKI, Municipality of Rače-Fram, Slovenia)	Cropland
Cropland	2023	Winter wheat	500 kg ha ⁻¹ NPK + 150 kg/ha KAN	-Herbicide: Lancelot 450 WG (Florasulam 150 g kg ⁻¹ + Aminopirid 300 g kg ⁻¹) (Corteva Agriscience, Zagreb, Croatia)	Cropland

2.3. Soil Sampling, CO₂ Concentration Measurement and Agro-Ecological Factors

Soil C-CO₂ emissions and sampling were measured four times during the year, using static chambers (replicates), in every season. Measurements were taken in 2021 during February, May, July, and November, and in 2023 during May, July, November, and December. At each measurement date, emissions from the eight chambers per land use type were recorded, and mean values were used for statistical analysis. The measurements followed the methodology described by authors using the in-situ closed static chamber method [7]. The chambers are made of lightproof metal, consisting of circular frames and

caps with gas sampling ports. After a 30 min incubation period, the CO₂ concentration was measured using a portable infrared CO₂ detector (GasAlertMicro5 IR, 2011; BW Technologies by Honeywell, Calgary, AB, Canada). The soil C-CO₂ emission (kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) was calculated according to the authors [41,42] on the basis of the following equation, which was determined by combining Fick's first law of diffusion and the equation-of-state of an ideal gas:

$$FCO_2 = [M \times p \times V \times (c_2 - c_1)] / [R \times T \times A \times (t_2 - t_1)]$$

where FCO₂ represents soil C-CO₂ emission (kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹); M—molar mass of the CO₂ (kg mol⁻¹); p—air pressure (Pa); V—chamber volume (m³); c₁—CO₂ concentration at the beginning of the measurement (μmol⁻¹); c₂—CO₂ concentration at the end of the measurement (μmol⁻¹); R—the gas constant (J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹); T—air temperature (K); A—chamber surface (m²); t₂ - t₁—incubation period (day) [7]. For each measurement of the CO₂ concentration, the soil parameters ((temperature (°C), moisture (%), electrical conductivity (mS m⁻¹)) were measured using the IMKO HD2 device with the Trime Pico64 (2011) probe (IMKO Micromodultechnik GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany). For each measurement of CO₂ concentration, two probes were inserted 10 cm deep into the soil near each chamber. Soil core sampling was performed at 0–10 cm depth in the vicinity of CO₂ measurements to determine bulk density, which was then used to calculate total porosity by methods described in the next chapter (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Measured parameters affecting soil C-CO₂ emissions under five land-use types.

2.4. Soil Analysis

The soil analyses were carried out according to the methodology and described using standardized laboratory protocols for a list of physicochemical parameters [43]. Total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (N) were determined using a CHN elemental analyzer (Vario Macro CHNS, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold, Germany, 2006). Carbon was measured by high-temperature combustion of finely ground soil in tin capsules, with organic carbon determined by subtracting inorganic carbon from total C content. Total nitrogen was quantified by combustion in the same analyzer, measuring the nitrogen released as gas. The available phosphorus was extracted using the Bray II (HCl and NH₄F, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) or Olsen method (NaHCO₃, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and quantified using the colorimetric ascorbic acid method [44]. The Olsen method was used for alkaline soils, while Bray II was used for acidic to neutral soils. Exchangeable potassium (K) was measured after triplicate extraction with 0.1 M BaCl₂ (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), followed by quantification by FAAS (AA-7000, Shi-

madzu, Kyoto, Japan) or ICP-OES (Avio 560 Max, PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). Soil pH was determined in a soil–water suspension at a ratio of 1:2.5 using a pH meter (ϕ 72 pH meter (Beckman), while electrical conductivity (EC) was determined in a soil–water extract at a ratio of 1:5 using a conductivity meter (Schott Lab 970, Schott Instruments, Mainz, Germany). Bulk density was calculated gravimetrically by measuring the mass of oven-dried soil and the volume displaced by it in a known container. Particle density was also calculated to determine the total porosity using the standard formula: $\text{Porosity (\%)} = [1 - (\text{bulk density} / \text{particle density})] \times 100$. Soil texture was analyzed using the hydrometer (ASTM 152H, Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) method based on sedimentation rates of particles in suspension. All measured soil parameters were determined to provide a basic characterization of the study area. These values are based on single-point measurements taken prior to the experiment and are not intended to represent seasonal or inter-annual variability. In contrast, soil physical properties and CO₂ emissions were monitored repeatedly across multiple seasons and years, as detailed in the relevant sections.

2.5. Data Analysis

The statistical software SAS 9.1. (SAS Inst. Inc., 2002–2004, Cary, NC, USA) was used to analyze the data. The effects of season, land use types, and their interaction on soil C-CO₂ emissions were evaluated using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). As the two measurement years (2021 and 2023) differed in climatic conditions, analyses were conducted separately for each year, resulting in two independent ANOVA models. When significant effects were detected, mean separations were performed using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test at the 5% significance level. The relationship between soil C-CO₂ emission and soil parameters such as soil temperature, soil moisture and soil porosity were analyzed using correlation analysis. The analysis was carried out separately for each of the two years. The strength of the correlation between soil carbon dioxide emissions and soil parameters was interpreted using the Roemer–Orphal scale [45]. The normality of variables was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Soil moisture and porosity (after Box–Cox transformation) showed normal distribution, while C-CO₂ emissions and soil temperature did not. Therefore, Spearman's rank correlation was applied to analyze relationships between variables.

3. Results

3.1. Effects of Season, Land Use, and Their Interaction on Soil C-CO₂ Emissions

Table 3 shows the results of the analysis of variance between seasons for each land use. In 2021, season had a significant effect on soil C-CO₂ emissions in forest, cropland, abandoned land and orchard ($p = <0.0001$), and in 2023 for all land uses (Table 3). The results of the variance analysis between the different land uses for each season show that in 2021 all seasons have a significant impact on soil C-CO₂ emissions, while in 2023 this applies to all months except winter (Table 4). Thus, Table 5 shows a seasonal change in soil C-CO₂ emissions with standard deviations during 2021 and 2023 across five types of land use—forest, cropland, grassland, orchard, and abandoned land. In 2021, in all land uses, the highest emissions were generally observed in spring and fall. In forested areas, the highest emissions were measured in fall (26.42 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), and the lowest in summer (14.22 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹). Similarly, cropland had the highest emissions in the fall (9.48 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), while significantly lower values were recorded in winter and summer (1.52 and 1.81 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹, respectively). Grassland recorded the highest emissions overall, especially in fall (610.0 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) and spring (566.6 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), with the lowest emissions in winter (383.0 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹). In orchards, emissions

were relatively stable throughout the growing season but dropped sharply during winter ($165.92 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$). On abandoned land, emissions peaked in fall ($16.94 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and spring ($14.36 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and fell in summer ($6.03 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$). Within each land use type, statistically significant differences were observed between seasons.

Table 3. Results of the analysis of variance between seasons for each land use (F value, Pr > F, R², LSD).

2021				
	F Value	Pr > F	R ²	LSD
Forest	37.02	<0.0001	0.798	2.82
Cropland	83.59	<0.0001	0.899	1.20
Grassland	0.78	0.515	0.077	326.99
Abandoned land	24.59	<0.0001	0.725	2.96
Orchard	15.48	<0.0001	0.624	69.08
2023.				
	F value	Pr > F	R ²	LSD
Forest	26.25	<0.0001	0.740	6.11
Cropland	25.20	<0.0001	0.730	7.41
Grassland	75.72	<0.0001	0.890	7.57
Abandoned land	23.78	<0.0001	0.718	5.22
Orchard	45.95	<0.0001	0.831	5.39

Table 4. Results of the analysis of variance between different land uses for each season (F value, Pr > F, R², LSD).

2021				
	F value	Pr > F	R ²	LSD
Winter	16.11	<0.0001	0.648	117.53
Spring	26.92	<0.0001	0.755	142.30
Summer	24.88	<0.0001	0.740	128.46
Fall	16.30	<0.0001	0.651	192.91
2023.				
	F value	Pr > F	R ²	LSD
Winter	4.22	0.0068	0.325	3.19
Spring	14.13	<0.0001	0.618	9.28
Summer	38.11	<0.0001	0.813	6.48
Fall	16.58	<0.0001	0.655	4.26

In 2023, all land use systems showed seasonal variation, with emission rates generally highest in spring and summer (Table 5). In forested areas, emissions reached their maximum in spring ($33.30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and summer ($30.47 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), with a significant decrease in fall ($19.84 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and especially in winter ($9.64 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$). For cropland, a clear seasonal trend was also observed, with emissions in spring ($33.59 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) being significantly higher than in all other seasons, especially in winter ($5.81 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and fall ($6.94 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), which had the lowest values. Of all the land use types analyzed, grasslands stood out with the highest emission levels, especially in spring ($54.84 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and summer ($52.98 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$). During the winter months ($11.62 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and fall ($17.52 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), these values dropped noticeably. On abandoned land, emissions were more consistent in spring ($24.23 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and summer ($22.39 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), with a marked decline in fall ($6.52 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$).

Similarly, orchards showed the highest values in spring ($36.85 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), with gradually decreasing emissions in summer ($29.19 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), fall ($17.54 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and winter ($11.05 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$).

Table 5. Seasonal values of average soil C-CO₂ emissions ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) with standard deviations in 2021 and 2023. Different uppercase letters represent significant differences between season for each land use ($p < 0.05$). Different lowercase letters represent significant differences between different land uses for each season ($p < 0.05$).

Forest		
	2021	2023
Winter	$18.24 \pm 2.26 \text{ Bc}$	$9.64 \pm 2.72 \text{ Ca}$
Spring	$25.70 \pm 1.72 \text{ Ac}$	$33.30 \pm 3.43 \text{ Acd}$
Summer	$14.22 \pm 2.29 \text{ Cc}$	$30.47 \pm 6.72 \text{ Ab}$
Fall	$26.42 \pm 3.63 \text{ Ac}$	$19.84 \pm 6.18 \text{ Ba}$
Cropland		
	2021	2023
Winter	$1.52 \pm 0.37 \text{ Cc}$	$5.81 \pm 2.30 \text{ Cb}$
Spring	$5.89 \pm 1.76 \text{ Bc}$	$33.59 \pm 12.22 \text{ Abc}$
Summer	$1.81 \pm 0.53 \text{ Cc}$	$15.59 \pm 3.92 \text{ Bd}$
Fall	$9.48 \pm 1.11 \text{ Ac}$	$6.94 \pm 3.60 \text{ Cc}$
Grassland		
	2021	2023
Winter	$383.0 \pm 240.1 \text{ Aa}$	$11.62 \pm 2.99 \text{ Ba}$
Spring	$566.6 \pm 288.2 \text{ Aa}$	$54.84 \pm 9.88 \text{ Aa}$
Summer	$487.0 \pm 252.9 \text{ Aa}$	$52.58 \pm 8.17 \text{ Aa}$
Fall	$610.0 \pm 390.0 \text{ Aa}$	$17.52 \pm 4.20 \text{ Ba}$
Abandoned land		
	2021	2023
Winter	$8.47 \pm 2.29 \text{ Bc}$	$10.20 \pm 3.76 \text{ Aa}$
Spring	$14.36 \pm 1.62 \text{ Ac}$	$24.23 \pm 7.26 \text{ Ad}$
Summer	$6.03 \pm 3.08 \text{ Bc}$	$22.39 \pm 4.38 \text{ Ac}$
Fall	$16.94 \pm 3.43 \text{ Ac}$	$6.52 \pm 2.25 \text{ Ac}$
Orchard		
	2021	2023
Winter	$165.92 \pm 31.76 \text{ Bb}$	$11.05 \pm 2.76 \text{ Ca}$
Spring	$366.65 \pm 53.96 \text{ Ab}$	$36.85 \pm 7.37 \text{ Ab}$
Summer	$309.83 \pm 78.18 \text{ Ab}$	$29.19 \pm 5.63 \text{ Bb}$
Fall	$362.41 \pm 76.73 \text{ Ab}$	$17.54 \pm 1.77 \text{ Cb}$

When comparing land use types within each season, significant differences in soil C-CO₂ emissions were found in both years (Table 5). In 2021, grassland recorded the highest emissions across all seasons, followed by orchard. Forest, abandoned land, and cropland had significantly lower values, with cropland having the lowest emissions overall. This pattern was consistent throughout the year. In 2023, grassland again had the highest emission rates, but the differences between land use types were less pronounced. Emissions from cropland, orchard, and abandoned land were generally higher compared to 2021. Although some differences were observed between years, grassland remained the land use types with the highest emissions, while cropland tended to have the lowest values.

Figures 4 and 5 show the average annual soil C-CO₂ emissions of the different land use types for the years 2021 and 2023, respectively. In 2021, grassland recorded the highest average soil C-CO₂ emission rate (511.64 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹). Orchards followed with a significantly higher emission level (301.21 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) compared to cropland, abandoned land, and forest, while the lowest emissions were observed in cropland (4.67 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹). Grassland also had the highest emissions in 2023 (34.15 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), which were significantly higher than those of all other land use types. This was followed by orchards (22.46 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), which had significantly higher emissions than cropland (15.48 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) but did not differ statistically from forest (21.56 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) and abandoned land (15.84 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹).

Figure 4. Average annual C-CO₂ emissions for each land use in 2021. Different letters represent significant differences between land uses ($p < 0.05$); LSD = 73.50.

Figure 5. Average annual soil C-CO₂ emissions for each land use in 2023. Different letters represent significant differences between land uses ($p < 0.05$); LSD = 6.79.

3.2. Seasonal Correlation Patterns of Soil C-CO₂ Emissions and Soil Properties in Different Land Use Systems

Figure 6 presents the seasonal correlations between soil C-CO₂ emissions and soil temperature, moisture, and porosity across various land use types in 2021 and 2023, evaluated using the Roemer–Orphal scale [45]. In forests, the strongest positive correlation between soil temperature and emissions occurred in spring 2023 ($r = 0.73$), while a very strong negative correlation was noted in fall 2021 ($r = -0.86$). Soil porosity showed a medium positive correlation in spring 2021 ($r = 0.36$) and a medium negative correlation in winter 2021 ($r = -0.47$), whereas in 2023 the correlations remained weak. Moisture correlations varied, ranging from strongly negative in summer 2021 ($r = -0.56$) to weakly positive in fall 2023 ($r = 0.27$). In cropland, soil temperature correlated most positively with emissions in summer 2023 ($r = 0.71$), whereas soil porosity had a pronounced negative correlation in fall 2023 ($r = -0.78$). Porosity showed almost no link in winter 2023 ($r = -0.02$). Soil moisture was mostly negatively correlated, except for a strong positive correlation in fall

2023 ($r = 0.80$) and a weak positive in winter and fall 2021. Grasslands exhibited the strongest positive correlation between porosity and emissions in winter 2021 ($r = 0.57$) and the strongest negative correlation between temperature and emissions in summer 2021 ($r = -0.71$). Porosity also showed a very weak positive correlation in spring 2021 ($r = 0.23$), while in 2023, values shifted to a medium negative correlation in winter ($r = -0.35$), while moisture correlations ranged from -0.62 to 0.25 between spring 2021 and winter 2023. On abandoned land, porosity correlated most positively with emissions in winter 2021 ($r = 0.43$), while temperature showed the strongest negative correlation in summer 2021 ($r = -0.61$). The weakest correlation in this category was between moisture and emissions in summer 2023 ($r = 0.01$). Overall, soil porosity tended to be moderately positively correlated with emissions, while soil temperature often showed negative correlations. In orchards, the highest positive correlation was between soil temperature and emissions in fall 2021 ($r = 0.63$), and the strongest negative correlation was between moisture and emissions in winter 2023 ($r = -0.49$). Porosity and emissions showed no meaningful correlation in spring 2023 ($r = -0.02$).

Figure 6. Correlation matrix of soil C-CO₂ emissions with soil temperature, soil moisture, and soil porosity across land use types and seasons (St—soil temperature (°C); Sm—soil moisture (%); Sp—soil porosity (%)).

4. Discussion

Soil CO₂ emissions are highly responsive to various environmental and management factors, particularly land use and seasonal fluctuations [46,47]. These fluctuations largely reflect dynamic changes in biological activity—such as root respiration and microbial decomposition—as well as variations in soil microclimate, including temperature and

humidity [3,48,49]. The results of this study show that soil C-CO₂ emissions vary significantly depending on land use types and season (Table 5). Of all land use types, grassland consistently recorded the highest emission rates in both study years, with seasonal peaks observed in spring and fall 2021, and spring and summer 2023. Although seasonal differences are evident, this emission pattern is primarily driven by land management and vegetation cover [50], especially continuous cover and mulching practices that promote a sustained input of organic matter and microbial activity [51]. These results are consistent with others [52,53], where authors [52] demonstrated that mulching and reduced tillage practices in Hungary maintained higher soil CO₂ concentrations compared to conventional tillage, due to improved soil moisture and enhanced microbial activity. Similarly, Birkás [53] emphasized that conservation tillage systems with residue cover tend to enhance soil respiration by improving the thermal and hydrological regime of the surface layer. These findings align with recent studies in grassland soils, where CO₂ emissions peak during warm and moist periods and decline under drier or cooler conditions [54]. The exceptionally high values in 2021 can be attributed to a local accumulation of easily degradable biomass, combined with favorable moisture conditions that enhanced microbial respiration [55,56]. This peak occurred only in 2021; in contrast, emissions in 2023 followed a more even seasonal distribution, with higher values in the first half of the year (from 54.80 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹) and a significant decrease in winter (to 11.62 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), likely due to excessive soil moisture reducing oxygen availability [57–59], especially in a year that received 41% more precipitation than the long-term average (Figure 2).

In contrast to grassland, which consistently had the highest soil C-CO₂ emissions, cropland recorded the lowest value across all seasons in 2021 during the soybean vegetation. However, in the winter wheat vegetation (2023), emissions from cropland increased significantly. These results can be attributed to the more extensive and fibrous root system of wheat, which promotes greater rhizosphere activity and microbial respiration [3,60,61]. Such root systems not only increase root surface area and exudate release but also improve soil aeration and the availability of organic substrate in the topsoil, thereby promoting microbial decomposition and CO₂ production [62,63]. In addition, a higher amount of mineral fertilizer applied in 2023 probably contributed to increased biological activity and thus soil C-CO₂ emissions [64,65]. The effect of mineral fertilizers on soil CO₂ emissions varies depending on the study [66–68]. Authors found that CO₂ emissions in cropland during the growing seasons were strongly correlated with root biomass and leaf area index, while tillage and fertilizer pulses at the beginning of the season significantly increased microbial activity [69,70]. In both years, soil C-CO₂ emissions were significantly lower in winter (6.94 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹–9.48 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), when the soil remained bare and there was no plant activity, confirming the key role of vegetation in maintaining biological processes in the soil [71,72]. This effect was also influenced by low soil temperatures (Figure 2), which suppressed microbial and root activity, as well as moisture conditions, where lower soil water availability in 2021 and excessive precipitation in 2023 contributed to limiting C-CO₂ emissions.

Forest soils, which are generally less disturbed and rich in organic matter, show a variable emission pattern that is influenced by seasonal and climatic factors (Table 5). In forests, carbon input comes mainly from leaf litter and root exudates [73]. This is consistent with our results from 2021, where emissions peaked in fall (26.42 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), likely due to the accumulation of fresh litterfall combined with favorable temperature and humidity conditions that favored microbial decomposition [74,75]. In contrast, the lowest soil C-CO₂ emissions were measured in summer (14.22 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹), indicating a possible temporary decrease in microbial activity due to lower moisture availability. These results differ from the emissions in 2023, [76,77], where the highest emissions were recorded in

spring and summer. These results can be attributed to warmer temperatures and higher soil moisture, which stimulated microbial and root activity earlier in the year. Such interannual variability observed over the two study years suggests that soil respiration in forests is highly responsive to changes in temperature and precipitation patterns, despite overall stability and low disturbance [78,79].

Although perennial vegetation is prevalent in both forests and orchards, the active management of orchards leads to additional factors that influence seasonal soil respiration. According to research [80], the storage capacity in orchards depends on climatic conditions, planting density, irrigation, and soil management. In 2021, relatively uniform values during the growing season ($309.83\text{--}366.65\text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{ day}^{-1}$) and lower emissions in winter ($165.92\text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{ day}^{-1}$) indicate sustained biological activity throughout the year. Some studies have reported similar results, where perennial orchards maintained high and stable soil respiration rates due to constant root turnover and organic matter input [81,82]. In contrast, emissions in 2023 were lower in all seasons, with a seasonal trend that peaked in spring, declined in summer and fall, and reached a minimum in winter. This remarkable decrease compared to 2021 could be a consequence of the higher precipitation in 2023, which may have led to increased soil moisture and partial waterlogging. This trend has also been confirmed by a study reporting reduced soil respiration with excessive moisture conditions in apple orchards [83].

Soil CO₂ emissions from abandoned land are generally lower than those from actively managed systems [84]. In this study, abandoned land had quite low and similar soil C-CO₂ emissions in both study years. The lower soil C-CO₂ emissions observed in 2021 and 2023 could be related to the absence of regular vegetation management and limited nutrient input, which likely reduced root activity and the availability of microbial substrates [85]. A similar pattern was observed by authors [86] who found that cropland abandonment in the North China Plain reduced soil microbial respiration. The brief increase in emissions in spring and summer 2023 may reflect a temporary boost in microbial and root activity stimulated by favorable moisture and temperature conditions. However, the subsequent decline in fall suggests that without active root turnover, litter deposition, or interventions that improve soil aeration and organic matter availability, microbial communities may remain underdeveloped or decline rapidly once environmental stimuli diminish [87]. In this context, the abandoned site, which has not been cultivated for about two decades and has undergone natural reforestation, could represent an early stage of secondary succession in which soil respiration remains limited due to the slow establishment of vegetation and incomplete recovery of soil structure and microbial communities.

Overall, the results confirm that both land use and seasonality strongly influence soil C-CO₂ emissions, and that their interactions are influenced by soil properties, vegetation cover, and management practices. These relationships have also been widely reported by other authors investigating the dynamics of soil respiration in different land use systems and under different climatic conditions [38,88–90]. While each system responded differently to climatic variability, it is evident that land use practices that maintain continuous plant cover and promote organic inputs to the soil are more effective in maintaining microbial activity and stable respiratory dynamics. This is also reflected in the average annual emission values, which integrate the seasonal variations into a clear overall picture: grassland and orchards had the highest annual emissions, while cropland had the lowest values in both years (Figures 4 and 5). The significantly lower annual values in 2023 also illustrate the sensitivity of soil respiration to interannual climate fluctuations, especially increased precipitation. The pronounced differences between 2021 and 2023 reflect not only the role of land use and seasonal dynamics but also strong inter-annual climatic variability. The drier 2021 (−11% precipitation compared to the referent period) limited microbial activity and

root respiration, whereas the wetter and slightly warmer 2023 (+41% precipitation, +1.1 °C) enhanced biological processes during spring and summer but suppressed winter emissions due to excessive soil moisture and oxygen limitation. Such opposing mechanisms illustrate why soil C-CO₂ emissions differed by more than an order of magnitude between years. Similar observations are reported by authors, where deviations in emissions exceed 39% even when average inter-annual variation is lower [91].

Soil temperature, soil moisture, and soil porosity are known to significantly influence respiration rates, but their effects can vary depending on soil management and climatic context [92,93]. Soil respiration occurs throughout the year, but its intensity varies seasonally depending on environmental conditions. In temperate climates, higher soil C-CO₂ emissions are generally recorded in spring and summer, when higher temperatures and favourable soil moisture promote microbial activity and organic matter decomposition [94,95]. Conversely, emissions tend to decrease in the colder months [96,97], which is due to lower biological activity and limited gas exchange under saturated or frozen conditions [98]. In this study, soil temperature was found to be the most consistent predictor of soil C-CO₂ emissions and showed strong positive correlations in spring and summer in several land uses, particularly in cropland and forest in 2023 as well as in orchards in summer (Figure 6). This pattern is consistent with the general finding that microbial respiration rates increase with temperature, provided that other conditions—such as moisture and oxygen—are not limiting [99,100]. However, the relationships were not uniform across years and land uses. For example, grassland in 2021 showed consistently negative correlations with temperature across all seasons, and in abandoned land, correlations shifted from positive in winter 2021 to negative in several seasons in 2023. (Figure 6). This finding aligns with other authors who also recorded negative trends under such conditions [101–104], suggesting that the usual positive effect of temperature on respiration may be reduced in saturated soils or low microbial activity. In contrast to temperature, the influence of soil moisture on soil C-CO₂ emissions was more dependent on the season and land use (Figure 6). While positive correlations were observed in some periods, negative relationships also occurred frequently, especially in forest (2021), cropland (2023) and abandoned land (2021) in almost every month. This variability reflects the dual role of moisture in regulating microbial respiration, where sufficient moisture is essential for microbial activity [105,106], while conversely, excessive water can inhibit aerobic decomposition [107]. These contrasting patterns in the relationship between soil moisture and CO₂ emissions have been widely reported by the literature [56,108,109]. In addition to the moisture availability, the soil physical condition, especially porosity, also plays an important role in regulating gas exchange and microbial habitat conditions [110,111]. In 2021, correlations were consistently positive across all seasons in grassland and abandoned land, possibly due to improved aeration in structurally stable soils (Figure 6). In 2023, positive associations became more widespread across land uses and seasons, including forest (spring, summer, fall), grassland (spring, summer, fall), abandoned land (spring, summer, fall), cropland (summer), and orchard (winter and spring). In contrast, the strong negative correlation observed on cropland suggests that tillage-induced changes in porosity may have negatively affected gas exchange [112]. Previous studies have shown that mechanical disturbance of the soil can reduce the number of interconnected pores, which restrict air and water movement and thus suppresses microbial respiration [49,113]. Even though soil porosity is not a primary factor for microbial activity, it can influence respiration by affecting the physical conditions of the soil, especially when other environmental factors are not limiting.

5. Conclusions

Land use management and seasonal climate variability have a significant impact on soil C-CO₂ emissions from peri-urban landscapes in central Croatia. Of the land uses analyzed, grassland and orchards tend to emit the most soil C-CO₂ annually and across seasons. This pattern is likely due to the continuous vegetation cover, root activity and abundant input of organic matter they receive. In contrast, croplands showed the lowest emission levels, which can be explained by intensive cultivation methods, the presence of bare soils, especially in winter, and consequently lower biological activity. Soil temperature generally remained the variable most strongly associated with soil C-CO₂ emissions, with pronounced correlations during the growing season primarily in croplands and forests, while orchards displayed weaker and less consistent associations. The effects of soil moisture and porosity were even more variable, showing moderate to weak correlations that shifted depending on both season and land use type. In particular, the differences between years, such as lower emissions in wetter years, highlight the sensitivity of soil respiration. These emissions are the result of a complex interplay between climate, soil properties and land management practices. A better understanding of the interplay between these factors can help to promote more sustainable approaches to land use. Good practices, such as absence of tillage and continuous vegetation, can effectively reduce carbon loss. These findings emphasize the important role that soil properties play in improving climate resilience and ensuring the long-term sustainability of land resources.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

ANOVA	Analysis of variance
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CHN	Carbon–Hydrogen–Nitrogen
EC	Electrical Conductivity
FAAS	Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry
ICP-OES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry
LSD	Last significant difference
KAN	Calcium Ammonium Nitrate
NPK	Nitrogen–Phosphorus–Potassium
R ²	R square
SAS	Statistical Analysis System
TOC	Total Organic Carbon

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